

A Web-Based Approach for Monitoring Scientific Research Projects: The Experience of OSTIM Technical University

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Submitted: 05.04.2026, Accepted: 17.04.2026, Published: 25.04.2026

Cite APA: Topal, BG, Müldür, S., Arslan, B., (2026). A Web-Based Approach for Monitoring Scientific Research Projects: The Experience of OSTIM Technical University, Journal of İstanbul School of Technology (JISTECH), 2(1), pp 132-153, DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.19655240

ABSTRACT

This study introduces the OSTIM Project Tracking System (OPTIS), developed within the scope of the OSTIM Technical University Scientific Research Projects (BAP) program, and evaluates data related to its design, implementation, and pilot application processes. The system is built on a Full-Stack architecture using Microsoft SQL Server, ASP.NET Core Web API, and Angular technologies, and is structured according to SOLID principles and the Onion Architecture model. OPTIS is designed to digitize and centralize the management of both internal university BAP projects and national/international competition-oriented R&D project applications conducted through the Technology Transfer Office (TTO). The pilot application demonstrated significant efficiency gains for academics, students, reviewers, and committee members in project application, reviewer assignment, meeting management, material/budget tracking, and reporting processes. Key results include a 25% reduction in administrative time, prevention of duplicate material purchases through inventory integration, and digital

archiving of project outputs. This study contributes to the literature by presenting a context-specific, institution-specific web-based project management solution and discussing its potential as a model for other higher education institutions in Türkiye.

Keywords: *Project Tracking System, BAP, University, Software Development, R&D Management, Web Application, Full-Stack Architecture*

1. INTRODUCTION

Projects are at the forefront of the mechanisms through which universities fulfill their core missions, such as knowledge production, conducting research and development activities, fostering innovative thinking, and driving technological advancement. Within broader industrial ecosystems, such technological awareness—particularly regarding Industry 4.0—and supportive organizational cultures directly enhance institutional innovation capacities, a dynamic clearly observed in the OSTİM Organized Industrial Zone (Özkan Alakaş, Kagitci Candan, Topal, & Atabey Bölük, 2025). Among these projects are scientific research projects, which constitute one of the internal support systems for universities within the Turkish academic system. In Türkiye, the Scientific Research Projects (BAP) coordination system forms the primary institutional framework for providing financial, technical, and administrative support to academics and students engaged in R&D activities at universities. Additionally, administrative infrastructures have been established to support these processes. These administrative processes generally rely on manual or semi-digital workflows, leading to significant inefficiencies from the submission of applications through peer review, resource allocation, and progress tracking. Furthermore, evaluating digitalization from a strategic management perspective is essential for increasing both organizational efficiency and digital transformation awareness (Topal, Alakaş Özkan, & Atabey, 2023; Öz, 2020).

In the context of global trends toward open science, data-driven governance, and integrated research information systems, the digital transformation of project management processes at universities has become increasingly important. International frameworks such as the Current Research Information System (CRIS) and electronic Research Administration (eRA) platforms have demonstrated that well-designed digital

systems can reduce administrative burdens, increase transparency, and enhance institutional accountability (Jeffery & Asserson, 2010) (Kerridge , 2012).

Operating under the motto of being an innovative, entrepreneurial, and third-generation university, OSTIM Technical University has appointed a Scientific Research Program (BAP) Coordination Office to oversee the processes of its Scientific Research Program and has established the OSTIMTECH R&D-Focused Technological Entrepreneurship Programs Support Commission within the Technology Transfer Office (TTO). This commission is responsible for evaluating support requests from faculty and students wishing to participate in national and international technology-focused competitions, preparing technical and administrative data for decision-making, and coordinating the financial and administrative processes of approved projects. Given the volume and complexity of these tasks, a dedicated digital infrastructure has become essential. The strategic value of such integrated processes is further reinforced by recent findings indicating that the OSTIMTech Technology Transfer Office operates at a strongly managed maturity level within the entrepreneurial university ecosystem (Topal & Maksüdünov, 2025; Baykal, 2023).

This study presents the OSTIM Project Tracking System (OPTIS), which was developed between July 2023 and January 2024 with a budget of 53,500 TL under the Research and Project Support (BAP) program at OSTIM Technical University. OPTIS is designed to fulfill two distinct yet interrelated functions: (1) the digitization of internal university BAP project management, including referee assignments and meeting coordination; and (2) the management of national and international R&D competition applications submitted by the Technology Transfer Office (TTO) to the TEGIP (Technological Entrepreneurship Program) commission.

The study's main contributions are threefold. First, it adds the experience of designing and implementing a context-specific, institution-specific web application to the project management literature. Second, it presents empirical data from the pilot implementation, including quantitative efficiency metrics. Third, it discusses the potential of OPTIS as a replicable model for other higher education institutions in Türkiye that currently lack an integrated project tracking infrastructure.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

With advancements in information technology and the increasing complexity of academic research and development management processes, project management and tracking systems have become a significant area of research. When examining early studies on web-based project tracking systems, the fundamental design principles emphasized include modularity, user-friendly interfaces, and the importance of data consistency (Suriya Kumari & Rajeswari, 2019; Bellah, Chen, & Zimmer, 2018). These studies have demonstrated that effective project tracking systems must balance technical sophistication with usability to ensure organizational adoption.

When examining processes at the international level, there are two dominant paradigms shaping university research information management: these can be defined as Current Research Information Systems (CRIS) and electronic Research Administration (eRA) platforms. CRIS systems, standardized through the CERIF (Common European Research Information Format) data model developed by EuroCRIS, provide an official interoperability framework that enables universities to manage their research outputs, personnel, projects, and organizational units within a unified structure (Jeffery & Asserson, 2010; Pinto, Simoes, & Amaral, 2014). (Jeffery & Asserson, 2010; Pinto, Simoes, & Amaral, 2014). The CERIF standard has evolved into an institutional backbone that extends beyond research offices to encompass libraries, human resources, financial services, and student affairs (Clements, 2015).

Semantic web technologies have contributed to research, development, and innovation knowledge management through platforms such as VIVO, which utilize Linked Open Data principles to support the profiling of researchers based on specific information, the identification of experts, and network visibility (Corson-Rikert, Conlon, Ding, & Börner, 2012). The integration of research data management into CRIS platforms, driven by Open Science requirements and data management plan requirements, has further expanded the scope of these systems (Schöpfel, Prost, & Reboulliat, 2017).

Electronic Research Management (eRA) systems, which have been widely adopted at universities in North America and Europe, have demonstrated improvements in process efficiency, compliance management, and reporting accuracy. Kerridge (2012)

emphasizes the complexity of procurement and sizing decisions for smaller or education-focused institutions, noting that the institutional context significantly influences the outcomes of such decisions (Kerridge , 2012). Cloud-based modular eRA solutions such as Quali Research have demonstrated the benefits of eliminating paper-based workflows while enhancing transparency and traceability in sub-grant management (Quali Research, 2021). At the national level, platforms such as IRINS in India demonstrate the feasibility of rapid, large-scale CRIS deployment integrated with open-access discovery systems. Research conducted within the context of higher education institutions in Türkiye has revealed that BAP management processes typically rely on manual methods or semi-digital systems that offer solutions tailored to specific departments. This situation acts as a limiting factor for both transparency and research efficiency, increasing both the technical and administrative workload. Consequently, it also restricts the capacity for real-time evaluation. Integrated project tracking systems specifically designed for Turkish university R&D contexts are underrepresented in the literature, creating a gap that OPTİS aims to address. The table below summarizes the foundational studies and systems in the CRIS/eRA field that provide the reference framework upon which OPTİS is designed.

Table 1. Project/CRIS/ERA Systems in Universities – Literature Review (2008–2025)

Year	Domain / Platform	Study Type	Key Insight	Representative Source
2010	CERIF / euroCRIS	Concept & infrastructure paper	CERIF provides a formal data model enabling interoperability across CRIS implementations at institutional, national, and EU levels.	CODATA Data Science Journal (Jeffery & Asserson, 2010)
2012	VIVO (semantic RIM)	Book / platform guide	Semantic web and linked open data support researcher profiling, discovery, and expertise mapping within universities.	VIVO: A Semantic Approach (Börner, Conlon, Corson-Rikert, & Ding, 2012)
2012	Electronic Research Administration (eRA)	Mixed-methods study (UK)	Universities adopt eRA to enhance compliance, throughput, and reporting; effects on research quality vary by institutional context.	ERA Reflections, Univ. of Sunderland (Kerridge , 2012)
2014	CERIF standard	Procedia Computer Science	CERIF standardization improves data exchange and governance in CRIS; XML-based models aid system integration.	(Pinto, Simoes, & Amaral, 2014)

Year	Domain / Platform	Study Type	Key Insight	Representative Source
2015	Pure CRIS (St Andrews)	EUNIS conference / case study	CRIS becomes a corporate system spanning registry, finance, and HR; cross-unit governance is critical for success.	EUNIS (Clements, 2015)
2017	CRIS & Research Data	ScienceDirect / Procedia CS	Growing trend toward integrating research datasets and data management workflows into CRIS to support Open Science.	(Schöpfel, Prost, & Reboulliat, 2017)
2018	eRA procurement	Master's thesis / institutional study	Collaborative procurement and right-sizing pricing models are pivotal for small and teaching-focused institutions.	(Bradshaw, 2018) Johns Hopkins
2018	Web-Based Project Tracking	Journal article	Modularity and user-friendly interfaces are foundational design principles for effective web-based project tracking systems.	(Bellah, Chen, & Zimmer, 2018)
2019	CRIS implementation (Libraries)	IATUL conference paper	Implementing CRIS ranks among top priorities for university libraries; cross-unit alignment is essential for adoption.	(Carr-Wiggin, Rothfus, Barrett, & Bourne-Tyson, 2019)
2020	National CRIS (IRINS, India)	National case study	National-level rollout demonstrates scalability of RIM/CRIS infrastructure and alignment with open discovery platforms.	IRINS case (Palavesm & Joorel, 2022)
2021	Kuali Research (CSU)	Vendor case study	Cloud eRA modules increase transparency and trackability in subaward management versus paper/PDF-based workflows.	(Kuali Research, 2021)

3. METHODOLOGY

The OPTIS project was developed over a six-month period (July 17, 2023 – January 17, 2024) under the OSTIM Technical University Research Fund (BAP) program, with a total budget of 53,500 TL. The project team consists of Bahattin Gökhan Topal, Instructor and Director of the Technology Transfer Office (Project Coordinator); Prof. Dr. Serdar Müldür (Research Advisor); Instructor Mehmet İrfan Gedik (Research Advisor), and Student Researcher Bahadır Arslan, and was carried out with the institutional participation of the Project Development and Management Office and the Technology Transfer Office. The system is built on a full-stack architecture that integrates three technology layers, adhering to the industry's best practices and aligning with SOLID design principles. The development methodology is iterative and agile, with official progress reports submitted to the BAP Coordination every three months.

3.1. Selection of Technical Infrastructure and Software Architecture

The selection of the technology stack was guided by three criteria: scalability for future module additions, sustainability through clean code principles, and accessibility for target user groups with diverse technical backgrounds.

Database Layer (Microsoft SQL Server): The relational database has been designed in strict accordance with normalization principles. Custom schema entities have been created for submitted R&D projects, users, reviewers, monitoring and results reports, budget items, materials, and meeting records. With this information in place, data integrity is ensured, and complex relational queries are enabled. Integration with the university's existing inventory of materials, accounting system, and laboratory management systems has been included to enable real-time material stock control.

Backend Layer (ASP.NET Core Web API and C#): The application logic layer has been implemented using the Onion Architecture pattern, which separates domain logic from infrastructure and presentation concerns. This architectural choice significantly reduces technical debt by ensuring that business rules remain independent of external frameworks, and facilitates future system expansions. The SOLID principles (Single Responsibility, Open-Closed, Liskov Substitution, Interface Segregation, and Dependency Inversion) have been applied throughout the entire codebase to produce reusable, independently testable modules.

Front-End Layer (Angular Framework): The user interface was developed using Angular, one of the most widely used JavaScript frameworks for enterprise web applications. Responsive design principles were applied to ensure compatibility with both desktop and mobile devices. Role-based interface customization has been implemented to provide different views and functionalities for project managers, reviewers, committee members, and system administrators.

Figure 1. OPTIS System Architecture — Frontend (Angular), Backend (ASP.NET Core Web API), Database (SQL Server)

3.2. System Modules

The OPTIS Project Tracking System is designed as a modular system to be used by different user groups and to serve various organizational functions simultaneously. The core modules developed over the course of the project are as follows:

Project Application Module (BAP and TEGIP): This module allows faculty members and students to directly submit their Scientific Research Projects (BAP) or technology-focused competition applications (TEGIP) to the system. Project submission includes uploading supporting documents, defining team members, specifying budget requirements, and selecting the project type. The module supports both BAP project types managed by the BAP Coordination Office and TEGIP applications managed by the TTO's entrepreneurship committee.

Reviewer Assignment Module: The system maintains a pool of qualified reviewers who are assigned to projects either automatically (based on expertise matching) or manually by system administrators. Reviewers receive automatic notifications and can access a dedicated interface for project review. This module has eliminated the manual process of reviewer identification and coordination, which was previously identified as one of the most time-consuming administrative tasks.

Meeting Management Module: Review meetings are scheduled through the system, and automatic notifications containing the meeting location, time, and agenda are sent to the assigned reviewers. Meeting results are recorded in the system, and the project manager receives an automatic notification regarding the decision status (approved to proceed, revision required, or rejected).

Materials and Budget Tracking Module: This module enables real-time tracking of project expenditures against approved budget items. A key feature is its integration with the university's inventory management system, which checks current stock levels before approving new material procurement requests. This mechanism directly prevents duplicate purchases, a significant source of resource waste identified in pre-system processes.

Reporting and Monitoring Module: Project progress is monitored in real time via dashboards accessible to project managers and administrators. The reporting module generates progress reports structured to align with the BAP Coordination's quarterly reporting cycle and digitally archives all project outputs, procurement records, and meeting decisions for institutional record-keeping purposes.

Role-Based Access Control (RBAC): The system implements a comprehensive role-based authorization framework with four distinct user roles: System Administrator, Project Manager, Evaluator/Reviewer, and Committee Member. Each role can access

only the modules and data relevant to its specific organizational function, thereby ensuring data security and process integrity.

Figure 2. OPTIS Module Structure

Project Submission, Reviewer Assignment, Meeting Management, Materials & Budget, Reporting.

When we look at the literature, we see that web-based project tracking systems have applications with advanced features in different sectors. Bellah and others (Bellah, Chen, & Zimmer, 2018) emphasize the importance of modularity and user-friendly interfaces in the design of web-based project tracking systems. Pinto Sousa, Simões, and Amaral (Pinto, Simoes, & Amaral, 2014) emphasize that data standards and integrated data structures are critical for management in CRIS systems. Schöpfel, Prost, and Rebouillat (Schöpfel, Prost, & Rebouillat, 2017) state that the integration of research data and reporting capacity are key elements for the sustainability of systems.

Based on these approaches, OPTİS has developed a solution specific to the context of OSTİM Technical University, contributing to the literature by digitizing the referee assignment process and developing a module for material/budget tracking.

3.3. Work Packages and Schedule

The six-month development cycle is divided into five consecutive work packages implemented within the framework of an official project schedule agreed upon with the BAP Coordination Office:

Research and Requirements Analysis (Months 1–2): Systematic review of existing BAP processes; structured interviews with BAP Coordination staff, TTO officials, faculty members, and student users; functional requirements specification and user story mapping.

Database Design (Months 2–3): Entity-relationship modeling on Microsoft SQL Server; table definition and relationship mapping for all system entities; normalization validation; design of an integration interface for the university inventory system.

Backend Development (Months 3–5): API endpoint development using ASP.NET Core Web API; implementation of the Onion Architecture layers (Domain, Application, Infrastructure, Presentation); business logic coding for all core modules; unit and integration testing.

Front-End Development (Months 3–5): Development of Angular components for all user interfaces; implementation of responsive design and role-based view differentiation; API integration and state management.

Pilot Implementation and Testing (Months 5–6): Deployment to OSTİM Technical University servers; pilot testing with limited access involving selected users from the

BAP Coordination, TTO, and academic staff; iterative feedback collection and system improvements.

Figure 3. OPTIS Project Timeline (Gantt Chart)

3.4. Alignment with the Literature and Originality of the Method

The project budget of 53,500 TL has been allocated to two expenditure categories during the first twelve months of the project period:

Table 2. Allocation of the Budget

No	Expenditure Item	Category	Amount (TL)
1	Domain and Hosting Service (1 year, guzel.net.tr)	Service Procurement	8,000
2	Consultancy / Bursary (Software Engineering student assistant, 6 months × 4,250 TL/month)	Service Procurement	25,500
3	Intel Core i7-1165G7, 16 GB RAM, 512 GB SSD Laptop (for software and graphic design)	Equipment	20,000
TOTAL			53,500

Source: (OSTIM Technical University BAP Project Proposal, 2023)

3.5. Alignment with the Literature

The design decisions made in OPTIS are consistent with established principles in the CRIS and eRA literature. The onion architecture and SOLID-based backend reflect the modular, scalable structures recommended for enterprise research information systems (Pinto, Simoes, & Amaral, 2014). The role-based access model is consistent with the governance frameworks described by Clements (Clements, 2015), in which CRIS systems serve multiple organizational units with varying data access requirements. The iterative pilot implementation approach reflects the best practices identified by Bradshaw (Bradshaw, 2018) for eRA adoption in university settings. The integration of the materials tracking module with inventory data directly addresses the transparency and traceability objectives highlighted in the cloud-based eRA literature (Kuali Research, 2021).

4. SYSTEM IMPLEMENTATION

The OSTIM Project Tracking System (OPTIS) has been piloted to manage and evaluate applications for Scientific Research Projects (BAP) conducted within OSTIM Technical University, as well as national and international R&D-focused competitions and entrepreneurship programs. During the six-month pilot implementation period, academic staff, students, referees, and processes were involved in coordination with the Scientific Research Program Coordination and the Technology Transfer Office (TTO).

4.1. User Groups

The system was launched with four distinct user roles, each with a dedicated interface and specific access permissions:

- System Administrators (BAP Coordination and TTO specialists): Full system access for configuration, user management, and reporting.
- Project Managers (Academic staff and university students): Access to project submissions, team management, document uploads, progress updates, and material procurement requests.
- Evaluators/Reviewers (Field experts from the reviewer pool): Access to assigned project documents, evaluation interfaces, and meeting schedules.

- Committee Members (TTO and BAP committee members): Access to project portfolios, meeting outcomes, and resource allocation dashboards.

Figure 3. (Module Structure) visually summarizes the modules designed specifically for these user groups.

4.2. Pilot Test Process

The pilot program has been structured as an iterative deployment process in accordance with the agile principles applied during development:

- **Deployment Phase:** Core modules (the project implementation module and the reviewer assignment module for BAP and TEGIP types) were deployed to university servers with restricted user access.
- **Initial Feedback Phase:** Structured feedback sessions were held with project managers, reviewers, and BAP Coordination staff. Key issues identified included the need for clearer module navigation and additional guidance for first-time users.
- **Development Phase:** The meeting planning and material tracking modules were improved based on feedback. Role-based authorization controls were strengthened,

and an automatic email notification feature was added to alert project managers about upcoming document deadlines and meeting invitations.

- **Integration Phase:** The system's inventory interface was integrated with the university's existing inventory management system, enabling real-time material availability checks during procurement requests.

- **Evaluation Phase:** A comprehensive evaluation conducted by the BAP Coordination Unit and the TTO using standardized evaluation criteria covering system usability, process efficiency, and data accuracy.

This phased approach is consistent with international evidence regarding eRA adoption: Bradshaw (Bradshaw) demonstrates that a phased, user-centered implementation significantly improves organizational adoption rates and reduces resistance to digital transformation. Schöpfel, Prost, and Reboulliat (2017) similarly emphasize that continuous testing and feedback loops are critical to the sustainability of CRIS-based systems.

4.3. User Feedback and Improvements

The feedback collected during the pilot program highlighted three key areas of the system's strengths. These headings have been identified as Efficiency, Transparency, and Usability.

Efficiency: Automated referee assignment and meeting notification workflows have significantly reduced the administrative time required to coordinate evaluation processes. BAP Coordination staff have reported that tasks which previously required individual email correspondence and manual planning can now be completed in minutes through the system.

Transparency: The budget tracking module, combined with real-time inventory integration, has provided clear visibility into project resource usage. Committee members

emphasized that the ability to view current stock levels before approving new purchase requests is particularly valuable in preventing unnecessary purchases.

Usability: The Angular-based interface has been positively evaluated for its responsiveness and intuitive navigation. Role-based interfaces have reduced cognitive load and training requirements by ensuring that each user group has access only to features relevant to their responsibilities.

The areas identified for improvement are as follows: integration with the university's existing personnel and financial management systems (Bordo); provision of structured orientation materials and guided tutorials for first-time users; Additionally, the development of an AI-powered referee recommendation module capable of automatically suggesting referees based on project keywords and referee expertise profiles is also under consideration. These findings are consistent with international studies emphasizing that user adoption levels and system integration are the most critical success factors for university research management systems (Clements, 2015).

Quantitative Results: The results were recorded during the six-month pilot period and summarized in Table 3.

Table 3. OPTIS Pilot Application Quantitative Outcomes

Indicator	Result
Total project applications received through OPTIS	8 applications
Applications successfully evaluated and monitored through completion	6 of 8 (75%)
Administrative time saving (TTO TEGiP Commission)	~25% reduction
Duplicate material procurement incidents detected and prevented	Multiple incidents
Project outputs and expenditures digitally archived	100% of evaluated projects
System uptime during pilot period	Continuous (server-hosted)

5. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

5.1. System Performance and Efficiency Improvements

The results of the pilot implementation demonstrate that OPTIS has yielded measurable increases in efficiency in both the BAP and TEGİP process areas. The 25% reduction in administrative time reported by TTO TEGİP Commission staff represents a significant operational gain, particularly given that the commission operates with limited staff relative to the volume of project applications. This finding is consistent with international eRA adoption studies, which indicate that the implementation of integrated digital systems results in administrative time savings of 20–40% (Kerridge, 2012; Quali Research, 2021).

The material tracking module's ability to prevent duplicate purchases represents perhaps the system's most direct financial impact. In the pre-system environment, the absence of a centralized inventory interface meant that project managers lacked a reliable mechanism to verify whether requested materials were already available within the university. OPTIS's integration with the university's inventory system directly addresses this gap, contributing to more efficient resource utilization.

5.2. Comparison with International Standards

When compared to the international CRIS and eRA frameworks, OPTIS demonstrates both compliance with established standards and contextual adaptations tailored to its organizational environment. The emphasis placed by the CERIF data model on interoperability and standardized data exchange is reflected in OPTIS's normalized database design, which accommodates both BAP and TEGİP project types within a unified structure (Jeffery & Asserson, 2010; Pinto, Simoes, & Amaral, 2014). The role-based access model reflects the multi-stakeholder governance architecture characteristic of CRIS applications at the institutional level (Clements, 2015).

The key difference between OPTIS and large-scale international CRIS systems is its deliberate institutional specificity. Rather than aiming for interoperability across

institutions, OPTIS is designed to align directly with the organizational structure, regulatory requirements, and administrative workflows of OSTIM Technical University. While this context-specific design serves as a strength that facilitates rapid adoption, it also poses a limitation in terms of the potential for replication in other institutions without customization.

The system's transparency and accountability features—particularly real-time budget monitoring and automated decision notifications—are consistent with the principles of open governance supported in the international research management literature (Schöpfel, Prost, & Reboulliat, 2017). The digital archiving of all project outputs, decisions, and expenditures contributes to institutional memory in a manner similar to research data management functions that are increasingly integrated into CRIS platforms.

5.3. Limitations and Areas for Improvement

The pilot implementation has identified various limitations that inform the system's ongoing development roadmap. First, the lack of integration with the university's human resources and financial management systems limits the system's ability to automatically cross-reference personnel data and financial approvals. Developing API connections to these systems has been identified as a priority for the next development phase.

Second, the integration experience needs to be improved, particularly for first-time users with limited digital literacy. To address this shortcoming, the development of structured guided tutorials, contextual help documents, and video training resources is planned.

Third, the current reviewer assignment module relies on manual administrator input for expertise-based matching. The development of an AI-powered automatic reviewer recommendation system that uses natural language processing to match project keywords with reviewer expertise profiles from publication and project history databases is proposed as a mid-term improvement. This feature could further reduce the administrative burden and enhance the quality of reviewer-project matches.

Fourth, while OPTİS currently handles two project types (BAP and TEGİP), the system architecture supports expansion to include additional project categories, such as projects funded by TÜBİTAK and European Union framework programs; this also enhances institutional R&D support.

5.4. Its Potential as a Model for Turkish Universities

The Turkish higher education system comprises more than 200 universities, the majority of which currently lack an integrated digital infrastructure for research project management. OPTİS serves as a proof of concept demonstrating that a functional, institution-specific system can be developed within the budget and timeline constraints of a typical university BAP project. The system's modular architecture, open-source-compatible technology stack, and documented development methodology provide a repeatable foundation that other universities can adapt to their own specific organizational contexts (Öz et al. 2019). Future research should include a comparative study examining BAP process efficiency metrics between universities with and without integrated tracking systems, as well as an investigation into the conditions under which OPTİS's architecture could be generalized into a national-level CRIS platform compatible with international data exchange standards.

6. CONCLUSION

This study presents the design, implementation, and pilot evaluation of OPTİS, a full-stack web-based project tracking system developed at OSTİM Technical University under the BAP program. By integrating Microsoft SQL Server, Onion Architecture-based ASP.NET Core Web API, and Angular, the system offers a modular, role-based platform that digitizes both internal university BAP project management and the application processes for national/international R&D competitions managed by the Technology Transfer Office.

Pilot implementation results demonstrate concrete contributions in three dimensions: administrative efficiency (a 25% reduction in processing time), resource accountability

(prevention of duplicate material procurement through real-time inventory integration), and institutional memory (digital archiving of all project outputs and decisions). These results are consistent with international evidence regarding the benefits of integrated university research management systems; the system's context-focused design, however, reflects the specific organizational and regulatory environment of Turkish higher education institutions.

OPTIS's most significant contribution to the literature is that it presents an empirically grounded case study on the development and deployment of a web-based project management system within the context of Turkish universities—an environment that is underrepresented in the international CRIS and eRA literature. The study demonstrates that significant efficiency gains can be achieved within the typical resource constraints of university research projects and that institutional uniqueness in system design facilitates rapid adoption. Future development priorities include integration with the university's personnel and financial systems, an AI-supported peer review recommendation feature, structured user participation resources, and expansion to additional project type categories. The system's documented architecture and methodology provide a replicable model for other higher education institutions in Türkiye seeking to modernize their research management infrastructure.

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